

The Influence of Electrolytes on the Solubilities of Some Organic Acids.

By

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It is well known that addition of small quantities of electrolytes and non-electrolytes influences the solubilities of various substances in water. Hans Ellen (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1899, 30, 360) and Rothamind (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, 33, 401) are among the recent investigators on the subject. Hoffmann and Lengbeck (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1905, 51, 385) found that the solubilities of organic acids were remarkably increased by the addition of small amounts of electrolytes but non-electrolytes produced no appreciable effect. The relative magnitude of the influence of the anions and cations of a few electrolytes was investigated by Max Levin (*Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1906, 56, 513), but no systematic study was made by him as well. Later on Bronsted (*J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 1448 *et seq.*) and Sidgwick and his pupils (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2819 *et seq.*), have studied the influence of orientation on the solubilities of different substances and also tried to explain the phenomenon of solubility.

In order to investigate the phenomenon more fully the authors have tried to make exhaustive study of the influence of various electrolytes as such and that of their anions and cations at varying concentrations and temperatures. Also they have examined whether the

behaviour shown by the acids as regards the solubilities in water is characteristic of the nature of the acids used, or is affected by their orientation and composition.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The acids used in the investigation were *o*-nitrobenzoic acid, *m*-nitrobenzoic acid, *p*-nitrobenzoic acid, *p*-aminobenzene sulphonic acid and *p*-hydroxybenzene sulphonic acid. The electrolytes selected were the sulphates, chlorides and nitrates of calcium, strontium and barium. The sulphates of the last three metals could not be tried as they are not soluble in water. The acids used were either "Merck's re-crystallized" or were prepared by the usual methods from the corresponding substances and purified by the standard methods. Other chemicals used throughout the investigation were "Becker's Purified Chemicals" of 99.998 per cent. purity. In this piece of research the purity of the chemicals and the cleanliness of the apparatus is of utmost importance as the solubilities are greatly affected by the presence of even traces of foreign substances. Scrupulous care was therefore taken in this direction. The apparatus was previously calibrated by the standard methods. The temperature of the thermostat was regulated by a mercury-toluene thermo-regulator.

A saturated solution of the acid under investigation was prepared in re-distilled water at 10 degrees above the temperature at which the solubilities were measured. When the solution was ready, 100 c.c. of this were transferred to each flask by means of a pipette (previously calibrated for that temperature) containing accurately weighed quantities of various electrolytes. The flasks were then corked and placed in the thermostat regulated at the temperature at which the solubilities were determined.

FIGURE I

FIGURE II

FIGURE I.

The solubilities were measured at three temperatures, 45°C, 35°C and 25°C in the case of the nitrobenzoic acids and at 40°C, 30°C and 20°C in the case of the sulphonic acids. In each case the temperature of the thermostat was carefully adjusted and the flasks were kept there for sufficient time to attain the temperature of the bath before the readings were taken. The solubilities were then determined by titrating the acid against standard alkali.

The solubilities of the acid in the absence of the electrolytes are taken to be 100—an arbitrary standard—and the solubilities of the acids in presence of varying amounts of the electrolytes are referred to that standard. Curves have been drawn with concentrations of the electrolytes and the solubilities as co-ordinates for various electrolytes and some of them are shown in Figures I, II and III.

In order to make a comparative study of the various electrolytes, their effect on the solubilities of *o*-nitrobenzoic, *m*-nitrobenzoic and *p*-nitrobenzoic acids was studied with the same molecular concentration of the electrolytes and at the same temperature and is described in Table IV.

Note.—Original solubilities of the nitrobenzoic acids under investigation as determined by the authors:—

	25°C.	35°C.	42°C.	
<i>Ortho</i> acid ...	0·750	1·30	2·28	per 100 gms. of water.
<i>Meta</i> acid ...	0·344	0·418	0·515	„
<i>Para</i> acid ...	0·028	0·025	0·022	„
Solubilities of <i>p</i> -aminobenzene				
sulphonic acid at 20°C.	30°C.	40°C.		„
	1·00	1·45	1·94	„

TABLE I.
o-Nitrobenzoic Acid. Temperature = 35° C.

Electrolyte used.	Molecular concentration.	Actual solubilities of the acid in 100 gms. of water.	Relative solubility of the acid.	Electrolyte used.	Molecular concentration.	Actual solubilities of the acid in 100 gms. of water.	Relative solubility of the acid.	Electrolyte used.	Molecular concentration.	Actual solubilities of the acid in 100 gms. of water.	Relative solubility of the acid.	Electrolyte used.	Molecular concentration.	Actual solubilities of the acid in 100 gms. of water.	Relative solubility of the acid.
Ammonium Sulphate	'0000	1:300	100'00	Ammonium Chloride	'0000	1:300	100'00	Ammonium Nitrate	'0000	1:300	100'00	Ammonium Nitrate	'0000	1:300	100'00
	'0016	1:245	95'79		'0040	1:256	96'56		'0028	1:313	101'03		'0028	1:313	101'03
	'0030	1:222	94'03		'0056	1:227	94'42		'0046	1:322	102'47		'0046	1:322	102'47
	'0060	1:191	91'56		'0079	1:199	92'26		'0082	1:337	103'87		'0082	1:337	103'87
	'0087	1:168	89'47		'0094	1:193	91'61		'0078	1:298	99'36		'0078	1:298	99'36
	'0082	1:136	87'36		'0117	1:171	89'80		'0093	1:252	96'92		'0093	1:252	96'92
Sodium Sulphate	'0000	1:300	100'00	Sodium Chloride	'0000	1:300	100'00	Sodium Nitrate	'0000	1:300	100'00	Sodium Nitrate	'0000	1:300	100'00
	'0014	1:296	99'65		'0041	1:241	95'44		'0026	1:318	101'40		'0026	1:318	101'40
	'0083	1:232	94'74		'0066	1:166	91'23		'0050	1:314	101'05		'0050	1:314	101'05
	'0063	1:154	89'56		'0094	1:126	86'66		'0077	1:297	96'79		'0077	1:297	96'79
	'0071	1:086	83'85		'0131	1:068	82'11		'0113	1:277	97'89		'0113	1:277	97'89
	'0078	1:072	82'46		'0155	1:040	80'00		'0137	1:260	96'14		'0137	1:260	96'14
Potassium Sulphate	'0000	1:300	100'00	Potassium Chloride	'0000	1:300	100'00	Potassium Nitrate	'0000	1:300	100'00	Potassium Nitrate	'0000	1:300	100'00
	'0015	1:310	100'70		'0081	1:296	94'49		'0028	1:321	107'02		'0028	1:321	107'02
	'0020	1:264	96'46		'0063	1:213	93'33		'0052	1:355	104'25		'0052	1:355	104'25

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'0038	1.181	90.88		'0089	1.181	90.48		'0088	1.219	101.45
'0046	1.088	84.21		'0088	1.149	88.42		'0139	1.272	97.94
'0071	0.881	76.48		'0112	1.084	78.77		'0181	1.281	94.08
			Calcium Chloride	'0000	1.8000	100.00	Calcium Nitrate	'0000	1.300	100.00
				'0016	1.334	102.59		'0017	1.715	131.93
				'0028	1.364	104.91		'0027	1.688	129.32
			Strontium Chloride	'0052	1.878	105.98		'0042	1.629	126.33
				'0089	1.332	102.46		'0080	1.616	128.51
				'0075	1.213	98.38		'0081	1.570	120.71
			Barium Chloride	'0000	1.800	100.00	Strontium Nitrate	'0000	1.300	100.00
				'0012	1.330	102.29		'0016	1.788	137.19
				'0021	1.385	105.02		'0025	1.763	134.74
				'0089	1.416	108.96		'0088	1.711	131.58
				'0040	1.464	112.68		'0042	1.676	128.92
				'0051	1.419	109.12		'0055	1.610	128.80
				'0000	1.800	100.00	Barium Nitrate	'0000	1.300	100.00
				'0012	1.388	108.80		'0015	1.680	140.70
				'0021	1.420	109.21		'0020	1.788	137.54
				'0081	1.485	114.28		'0024	1.764	134.90
				'0040	1.510	116.14		'0088	1.677	128.22
				'0055	1.464	112.68		'0045	1.570	128.08

TABLE II.

m-Nitrobenzoic Acid.

Temperature = 35° C.

Electrolyte used.	Molecular concentration.	Actual solubilities of the acid in 100 grms. of water.	Relative solubility of the acid.	Electrolyte used.	Molecular concentration.	Actual solubilities of the acid in 100 grms. of water.	Relative solubility of the acid.	Electrolyte used.	Molecular concentration.	Actual solubilities of the acid in 100 grms. of water.	Relative solubility of the acid.
Ammonium Sulphate	·0000	·418	100·00	Ammonium Chloride	·0000	·418	100·00	Ammonium Nitrate	·0000	·418	100·00
	·0017	·3105	76·70	·0086	·2048	48·88	·0088	·2189	·0088	·1718	41·11
	·0080	·2598	64·44	·0080	·1950	46·68	·0049	·1593	·0049	·1593	37·41
	·0048	·2616	63·69	·0078	·1896	45·85	·0089	·1315	·0089	·1315	31·45
	·0064	·2654	61·11	·0100	·1880	43·70	·0082	·1160	·0082	·1160	27·77
	·0097	·2446	58·52	·0146	·1673	40·00	·0000	·418	·0000	·418	100·00
Sodium Sulphate	·0000	·418	100·00	Sodium Chloride	·0000	·418	100·00	Sodium Nitrate	·0000	·418	100·00
	·0020	·8285	77·41	·0070	·2059	49·26	·0018	·2199	·0018	·2199	52·68
	·0082	·2848	68·15	·0088	·1808	45·55	·0082	·1842	·0082	·1842	44·07
	·0061	·2771	68·80	·0125	·1718	41·11	·0057	·1895	·0057	·1895	38·88
	·0078	·2687	64·80	·0171	·1496	36·55	·0078	·1449	·0078	·1449	34·44
	·0089	·2616	62·69	·0287	·1283	29·26	·0101	·1254	·0101	·1254	30·00
Potassium Sulphate	·0000	·418	100·00	Potassium Chloride	·0000	·418	100·00	Potassium Nitrate	·0000	·418	100·00
	·0016	·8317	79·87	·0083	·2387	55·98	·0017	·2548	·0017	·2548	60·98
	·0087	·2687	71·48	·0076	·2218	53·96	·0082	·1998	·0082	·1998	47·77

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.0089	.2886	70.74	.0116	.2080	50.00	.0063	.1780	43.69
.0045	.2810	89.63	.0164	.1981	47.41	.0071	.1633	37.41
.0063	.2848	68.15	.0197	.1887	44.44	.0063	.1408	33.70
			.0000	.418	100.00	.0000	.418	100.00
			.0023	.2625	60.41	.0016	.2427	58.07
			.0088	.2668	56.66	.0083	.2290	54.80
			.0068	.2291	54.81	.0043	.2215	53.91
			.0085	.2239	53.83	.0060	.2187	53.38
			.0113	.2408	57.48	.0085	.2161	51.71
			.0000	.418	100.00	.0000	.418	100.00
			.0010	.2850	63.41	.0012	.2363	56.55
			.0017	.2430	58.15	.0023	.2284	54.96
			.0025	.2354	57.04	.0028	.2244	53.70
			.0039	.2349	56.19	.0030	.2161	51.70
			.0040	.2270	54.33	.0031	.2140	51.22
			.0000	.418	100.00	.0000	.418	100.00
			.0013	.2675	64.00	.0013	.2343	66.06
			.0018	.2623	60.37	.0018	.2326	56.90
			.0024	.2446	53.52	.0024	.2330	54.80
			.0033	.2399	57.41	.0033	.2225	53.43
			.0041	.2668	56.45	.0041	.2302	53.70

Calcium Nitrate

Strontium Nitrate

Barium Nitrate

Calcium Chloride

Strontium Chloride

Barium Chloride

TABLE III.
p-Nitrobenzoic Acid. Temperature = 36° C.

Electrolyte used.	Molecular concentration.	Actual solubilities of the acid in 100 gms. of water.	Relative solubility of the acid.	Electrolyte used.	Molecular concentration.	Actual solubilities of the acid in 100 gms. of water.	Relative solubility of the acid.	Electrolyte used.	Molecular concentration.	Actual solubilities of the acid in 100 gms. of water.	Relative solubility of the acid.
Ammonium Sulphate	·0010	·025	100·00	Ammonium Chloride	·0000	·025	100·00	Ammonium Nitrate	·0000	·025	100·00
	·0281	·027	108·00		·0023	·046	138·54		·0047	·0402	180·69
	·0042	·028	110·69		·0084	·0863	141·23		·0085	·0413	165·08
	·0087	·089	117·92		·0103	·0852	140·92		·0103	·0414	166·77
	·0102	·0895	117·85		·0137	·0843	137·31		·0137	·0405	162·08
·0125	·089	116·54	·0178	·0320	128·00	·0165	·0386	158·33			
Sodium Sulphate	·0000	·025	100·00	Sodium Chloride	·0000	·025	100·00	Sodium Nitrate	·0000	·025	100·00
	·0018	·0269	107·77		·0035	·0868	143·38		·0038	·0405	163·00
	·0040	·0286	115·46		·0135	·0655	142·06		·0070	·0417	164·69
	·0051	·0806	120·15		·0152	·0853	141·36		·0084	·0418	167·38
	·0076	·0809	123·85		·0184	·0347	138·68		·0112	·0413	165·23
·0102	·315	126·04	·0257	·0824	129·85	·0144	·0401	166·77			
Potassium Sulphate	·0000	·025	100·00	Potassium Chloride	·0000	·025	100·00	Potassium Nitrate	·0000	·025	100·00
	·0017	·0272	108·77		·0035	·0328	131·38		·0028	·0386	153·50
	·0037	·0281	113·46		·0049	·0342	137·08		·0052	·0414	165·69

TABLE IV.

Comparative solubilities of the nitrobenzoic acids containing the same groups in different positions under the same conditions.

Molecular concentration = .0011. Temperature 35°C.

Electrolyte used.	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid.	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid.	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid.
Ammonium Sulphate ...	97.0	94.2	103.0
Ammonium Chloride ...	99.0	87.0	107.6
Ammonium Nitrate ...	100.4	81.7	114.0
Sodium Sulphate ...	98.9	91.2	104.2
Sodium Chloride ...	99.4	86.8	107.9
Sodium Nitrate ...	100.9	76.9	118.6
Potassium Sulphate ...	100.1	85.0	105.2
Potassium Chloride ...	100.5	84.5	109.9
Potassium Nitrate ...	102.8	75.5	125.0
Calcium Chloride ...	101.3	81.4	115.9
Calcium Nitrate ...	120.4	71.9	149.0
Strontium Chloride ...	102.3	65.4	128.0
Strontium Nitrate ...	125.7	63.7	150.4
Barium Chloride ...	106.2	62.4	129.6
Barium Nitrate ...	109.0	61.8	157.7

Discussion of Results.

A reference to the tables and graphs shows that the addition of electrolytes has a marked effect on the solubilities of these organic acids. There is a marked regularity in the decrease or increase of the solubilities as the concentration of the electrolytes is increased. The various conclusions that may be drawn from the foregoing experiments may be briefly stated as follows:

1. *The Influence of Temperature.*—With the increase in temperature, the influence of the nitrates and chlorides of alkali metals in increasing or decreasing the solubilities of the acids decreases, but that of the nitrates and chlorides of the alkaline earth metals increases as the temperature rises. These observations are clearly shown in the case of *p*-nitrobenzoic acid in Figure III. Similar curves were obtained in the case of other acids as well. The solubility of the *meta*-acid in the presence of electrolytes does not show much variation with the change in temperature. But in general there is an increase in the solubilities of the acids with the rise in temperature.

2. *The Influence of Electrolytes.*—The solubilities of the *ortho*- and *para*-acids first increase with the increase in the concentrations of the electrolytes used, reach a maximum and then decrease with the increasing concentrations (*cf.* Graphs I and II). The maximum increase in the solubility of the acids is different with different electrolytes. The solubility of the *meta*-acid decreases first rapidly and then slowly and regularly as the concentration of the electrolytes is raised.

3. *The Influence of the Basic Radicles.*—The basic radicles of the electrolytes show an extraordinary regularity in their effect on the solubility of the acid. As the

atomic weight of the basic radicles of the electrolytes increases, there is an increase in their effect on the solubility of the acids as well. The same influence is observed in the case of *meta*-acid, but instead of increase there is a decrease in the solubility in the same order. The various basic radicles employed may, therefore, be represented in order of their influence on the solubilities of the acids as follows :

This order is the same as that of their atomic weights. From this we may conclude that the divalent positive radicles have a greater influence than the monovalent ones.

4. *The Influence of the Negative Radicles.*—The negative radicles of the various electrolytes also seem to exert a definite effect on the solubility. The effect of the nitrates of different metals on the increase in the solubilities of the acids is far greater as compared to the effect exerted by the corresponding chlorides in the same molecular concentration. Similarly the effect of the chlorides is greater than that of the sulphates. Thus the order of the groups of acid radicles with regard to the increase of the solubility may be written as

The *meta*-acid is also influenced by the acid radicles in the same order—the nitrates decreasing the solubilities of the acid most and the sulphates least, the chlorides standing between the two.

5. *The Influence of the Orientation of the Acid.*—From the tables and graphs we find that the orientation of the acids plays an important part in the effect produced in their solubilities by various electrolytes. The effect of the addition of electrolytes on the solubilities of the

ortho- and the *para*-acids is similar to one another, but the maxima obtained in the case of the *para*-acids have higher values to those obtained in the case of *ortho*-acids. The *meta*-acid on the contrary shows quite abnormal results as compared to the *ortho*- and the *para*-acids. In the case of the *ortho*- and *para*-acids the solubility first increases and then decreases but in the case of the *meta*-acid, the solubility continuously decreases.

6. *The Influence of the Composition of the Acids.*—The composition of the acids too has got some significance in this effect. The order in which their solubilities are affected are almost the same but the degree of this effect varies. The stronger acids are influenced to a greater extent than the comparatively weaker ones. The acids with a nitro group in their composition are most influenced than the acids with an amino group and they in turn are more effected than the acids with hydroxyl group in their molecule.

As regards the mechanism of the phenomenon nothing can be definitely stated in absence of any conclusive evidence. Harkins, Brown and Davis (*J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 354) have tried to explain the solubility of various substances in water on considerations based on free energy decrease which is more or less a measure of the attraction of the active groups of the solute for the solvent molecules, and which to a secondary extent depends upon the shape and size of the molecules. According to them the solubility is a molecular scale phenomenon and is dependant upon the attraction of the different parts of the various molecules for each other and upon the shape and sizes of the molecules which must be fitted together to make a solution. However it is not very clear what would be the mechanism of the influence produced on the solubility of the acids by the addition of small quantities of electrolytes, and it is difficult to

understand how exactly the addition of the same quantity of the same electrolyte to the same acids having the same groups but different orientation should produce different effects. The authors think that it may probably be due to the formation of molecular complexes or some chemical interaction between acids and the electrolytes. Further experiments on viscosity, conductivity and absorption spectra are in progress in this laboratory.

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Investigations on the Acid Nature of some Derivatives of Sulphur, Selenium and Tellurium.

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Four principal methods were used by Hantzsch in supporting his extended theory of pseudo-acids. They have already been referred to in a previous paper (this *Journal*, 1925, 1, 247) and it has been shown that, according to the new theory, it was the "ionogen" bond between the "acid" hydrogen atom and the acid radical which was responsible for the acid properties and not the concentration of the hydrogen ion, as was supposed